

Research Article

VARIABILITY OF MEDICAL TERMS AND MINIMIZING IT IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Linguistics

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Abstract

In this article, practical recommendations are given regarding the concept of variant and the phenomena of variant, which appear in the terminology, as well as ways to eliminate them. In addition, in linguistics, the issue of variation, ways of its appearance and types are interpreted differently by experts, including three types of variation in the language, such as morphological, phonetic, and colloquial variants. In order for the works to be reliable and effective, it is thought that the phenomena of synonymy, doublet and variant should be studied in the framework of separate studies, and the boundaries between them should be separated. In this article, due to the emergence of a new concept in any field and the need to express it in the language, the emergence of variants is a natural process at the first stage of the formation of terms, and in this sense, variant terms, like doublets, are often found in field terminology, especially in medical terminology proved on the basis of concrete examples. However, the existence of variability in the terminology is not positively evaluated. Therefore, it is said that it is possible to achieve a certain result by increasing the number of studies that serve to expand the range of use of the word, without continuing the variation.

The concept of variantness entered linguistics in the 17th century and has been studied to varying degrees in many languages. For example, the study of this phenomenon in Russian linguistics began in the 40s and 50s of the last century. V.V.Vinogradov, A.I.Smirnitsky, O.S.Akhmanova and other famous scientists think about the theoretical issues of variantism.

Terminologist N.Qasimov writes as follows under the title “Orthographic synonyms”. “Among the technical terms, there is also synonymy, which expresses the same concept in content, but is written differently. Most of these terms belong to compound and compound terms. For example, *air blower - air blower, water meter - water heater*. It is better to add the components of such terms and write them in the form of a compound term. Because they are the expression of a single concept. In this case, orthographic variation in terminology will be eliminated¹. “Although the author has put the title “orthographic synonyms”, he ends the sentence with “orthographic variation (not *orthographic synonym*) will be eliminated”.

It seems that even in the works devoted to terminology, the issue of variantness has not been seriously considered. When guidance was given on matters of arrangement of terms, only the occurrences of synonymy or doublet were analysed. Sometimes variant terms were analyzed mixed with synonymous or doublet terms. In general, “synonym, doublet, and variant phenomena

¹ Kasimov N. Synonymy in Uzbek technical terminology and ways to eliminate it / lexical options in Uzbek terminology. Tashkent: Science, 1986. Pp. 63-78.

are not sufficiently processed in linguistics. There is no uniformity in describing their similar and different signs and specific signs of these phenomena².

Therefore, in order to be reliable and effective, the phenomena of synonymy, doublet and variant should be studied in the framework of separate studies, and the boundaries between them should be distinguished. Only then, the work done on the regulation of terms, the given recommendations will have their practical effect.

When studying the issue of variantness in linguistics, the ways and types of its emergence were interpreted differently by experts. In particular, O.S. Akhmanova divides language variants into three types, such as morphological, phonetic and colloquial language variants³.

R.P. Rogojnikova analyzes variants by grouping them into only two types - phonetic and morphological variants⁴.

Variant terms found in Uzbek medical terminology were divided into phonetic and morphological variants based on these principles.

Phonetic options . When analyzing the vocabularies of the *field*, *alahlamak - alaklamak*, *alahsimak - alaksimak*, *bukrilik - bukirlik*, *govmijja - govmichcha*, *yod - iod*, *collapse - collapse*, *neuron - neuron*, *seizure - convulsion*, *khadakan - sadakhan*, *decay - caused by certain phonetic phenomena* . It is observed that there are alternative terms such as *irish*, *hukna - hukna*, *khoppoz - khoppoz* .

In order to check which of these terms is the correct option, dictionaries related to the field and the materials of "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" were comparatively studied. In particular, when analyzing the variants of the terms *bukrilik - bukirlik* , *it can be seen* that in some dictionaries related to the field, among these units , the term *bukrilic* is given as the main term, and *bukirlik* is given as its variant,⁵ and in some of them, *bukrilic* is recorded as the main term⁶ . Also, in the five-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" it is possible to see that the term *scoliosis* was chosen to express this concept and it was explained in the form of "bulging out of the spine as a result of laziness or various diseases". However , although the dictionary does not give the option of *bukur* , *the base of this word, that is, the word bukur* , is given an explanation with a similar meaning:

BUKUR 1 A bulging, curved area formed by the curvature of the spine or chest (Vol. 1, p. 369).

bukrili as the main term among these options.

² Mukarramov M. Scientific style of modern Uzbek literary language. Tashkent: Science, 1984. P. 58.

³ Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. Москва, 1966. С. 71.

⁴ Рогожников Р.П. Варианты слов в русском языке. Москва, 1966. С. 65-75.

⁵ Medical encyclopedia. Tashkent: Komuslar General Editorial Office, 1994. P. 65.

⁶ Encyclopedia of Medicine. Tashkent: Sharq, 2016. P. 76.

Also, in the explanatory dictionary, the variant of *seizure* and *seizure* units is also indicated:

SEIZURE 1. *tib.* An incurable nervous disease, with periodic sudden seizures, in which a person faints and becomes akashak; rabbit, epilepsy. *Salim's panic attack started again. The child is very nervous.* A. Mukhtar, Chinor.

2. Such a sick person.

EPILEPSY sv. Seizure, rabbit. *The owners laughed at the mirab: "Your dog has a seizure."* J. Sharipov, Khorezm (Vol. 4, p. 212).

So, it is clear that the term *seizure* is the main option *here*. Accordingly, it is positive that only the term "seizure" is recorded in the field *dictionaries*.

Another variant of such terms is *govmijja* and *govmichcha* lexical units. In the medical literature, these options are described as "acute purulent inflammation of the sebaceous glands and eyelash follicles" in various medical literature and dictionaries, and in general philological dictionaries, sometimes they are given as⁷ *govmichcha*, *sometimes govmijja*. In the five-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" only the term *govmijja* is given (this case also corresponds to the Persian spelling of the word variant). Based on this, we recommend to give only the term *govmijja* from these variant units in the field dictionaries.

Morphological options. Morphological options are formed by additions that have a mutual meaning.

gar and *– shunos* have formed variant terms in the units *dorigar-pharmacist*. Both terms are noted and explained accordingly in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language". However, taking into account that the range of use of the term "pharmacologist" "has expanded among these options in modern medical terminology, we recommend using this option and giving it as the main term in field terminological dictionaries.

Also, the affixes *– lik* and *– chilik* also *created* variant terms such as *midwifery – midwifery*. In some specialized dictionaries, you can see that *midwifery* is the main term, and *midwifery* is given as its variant. Both terms are given in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language". If only the *midwifery* option is interpreted as the main term, the term *midwifery* is "recorded with the symbol "midwifery" (Volume 1, page 651). In fact, the term *obstetrics in Russian is translated* into Uzbek as *midwife*.

⁷ Russian-Uzbek medical dictionary. Volume II. Tashkent: Medicine, 1971. P. 454; Medical encyclopedia. Tashkent: Komuslar General Editorial Office, 1994. P. 68; Encyclopedia of Medicine. Tashkent: Sharq, 2016. P. 137.

There are some variant terms in the field that require a slightly different approach. Here are some examples of such options. In field dictionaries, *neuron is mentioned* as the main term in neuron-neuron *variation*, and it is called “1. Nerve cell, which is represented as a structural unit of the nervous system; 2. It is explained in the style of “axon”, and in the explanation of the term *neuron*” *q.* you can see a note like “**neuron**”⁸. We cannot say that any of these option units are wrong. Because both of them were created with a certain scientific basis. L.V. Shcherba also commented on such terms, “Most of the time, both options are considered the same or to a certain extent correct”⁹. “Sometimes it is necessary to call both options the norm”¹⁰, writes E.S. Istrina, confirming this opinion. Therefore, we recommend that these units be given in dictionaries as mentioned above.

Options such as autolysis – autolysis, venopuncture – venepuncture, venosection – venesection, hidradenoma – hydroadenoma, hydrarthrosis – hydroarthrosis can also be included among the terms, both of which are correct, as above.

Thus, variation, that is, the parallel use of means of expression with the same lexical meaning, is the result of the development of our language, at the same time, it is the appearance of old and new features¹¹.

Due to the emergence of a new concept in any field and the need to express it in the language, it is a natural process that variants appear at the first stage of the formation of terms. In this sense, in medical terminology, like doublets, variant terms are often found. However, the presence of variability in terminology is not appreciated. Therefore, it is necessary to choose a term that can fully meet the requirements of the term, and to recommend and accept this term as an acceptable term without continuing the option¹². The most important thing is to choose the term that expresses the most characteristic aspect of the concept or subject, its function, social essence and value.

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⁸ Russian-Uzbek medical dictionary. It has two roofs. Volume II . Tashkent: Medicine, 1971. P. 15 and 18.

⁹ Щерба Л.В. Опыт общей лексикографии / Известия АН СССР, 1940. № 3. С. 97.

¹⁰ Истрина Е.С. Нормы русского литературного языка и культура речи. Москва, 1948. С. 5.

¹¹ Горбачевич К.С. Изменение норм русского литературного языка. Л.: Наука, 1971. С. 20.

¹² Hojiev A. Term selection criteria. - Tashkent: Science, 1996. - P. 18.

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